

VARIOUS APPROACHES AND ACTIVITIES OF TEACHING ANTONYMS IN MODERN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The article provides information about antonyms, its types, and how to teach them through interactive methods of teaching to school students during the English class, which leads to improve their critical thinking, fast response and active participation as well as enhance their outlook. Furthermore, the article contains some thoughts and approaches expressed by famous linguists.

Key words: *Antonyms, opposite name, good-bad, tall-short, night-day, laugh-cry, unique approach.*

Introduction:

Antonyms are a must learning part of English grammar. Every student should get to the point of this feature in order to be able to use a wide range of vocabularies in the learned language. In this article, there will be given a chance to be more familiar with antonyms by doing interactive activities thoroughly.

Daniel Bal who has a Master's degree in both English and philosophy considers that antonyms are words with opposite meanings. The word antonym comes from Greek and means "against a name." There are three types of antonyms, and many words can have multiple antonyms, depending on the meaning of the original word. As literary devices, antonyms are one of the simplest to find and use. [1]

Richard Nordquist at Georgia Southern University points out that an antonym is a word having a meaning opposite to that of another word such as *hot* and *cold*, *short* and *tall* and another word for antonym is counterterm. Antonym is the sense relation that exists between words which are opposite in meaning. [2]

Alexa Barta claims that antonyms are important both in reading and in writing because they help people to discern the meaning of an unfamiliar word. By looking at the word's antonym, often the definition of the unfamiliar word becomes clear. [3]

Charlotte Guest is the opinion of expanding and improving one's English vocabulary can be done in various ways, but exploring antonyms can be a handy and unique approach. Antonyms, which are words that express opposite meanings, can help a learner enhance their language skills. Knowing a wide range of them can be incredibly helpful in everyday life and help one get their point across clearly.[4]

Antonyms are pretty obvious, like "good" and "bad," or "black" and "white." Some words can be transformed into their *antonyms* simply by adding the prefixes "un," "in," or "non," as when "likable" is changed into its antonym, "unlikable." The word *antonym* itself takes the Greek word *anti*, meaning "opposite," and adds it to *-onym*, which comes from the Greek *onoma*, or "name." So *antonym* literally means "opposite-name." [5]

Understanding antonyms can also improve a student's word choice so they become a more effective communicator. For example, instead of describing a character as "not nice," a learner could research antonyms for "nice" and instead describe them as "unpleasant." Or, instead of describing a character as "not very smart," they could describe them as "obtuse." [6]

It is critical to underline at last the way that antonyms are a fundamental part of the day by day correspondence in various circumstances. As the cases above appeared, antonyms are utilized to separate implications of sentences and their structures and are a wellspring of new method for correspondence. Despite the fact that they are semantically clarified, each second dialect learner of English dialect must know when utilizing them furthermore exceptionally mindful when attempting to get their importance. Because of the utilization in reporting and a wide range of media, which a decent wellspring of taking in a brief moment dialect, in English dialect they are all that much used for various adjustments of expressions. The way they are utilized are diverse in numerous dialects and the significance, without seeing the best possible esteem here and there, is expanded when utilizing the language every day. [7]

The list of antonyms

1. Day – night
2. On – off
3. Entrance – exit
4. Exterior – interior
5. True – false
6. Alive – dead
7. Pass – fail
8. Borrow – lend
9. Give – receive
10. Buy - sell
11. Teacher – pupil
12. Hard – easy
13. Wise – foolish
14. Fat – slim
15. Warm – cool
16. Early - late
17. Fast – slow
18. Lead – mislead
19. Agree – disagree
20. Excusable – inexcusable
21. Able – unable
22. Sense – nonsense
23. Lucky – unlucky
24. Fortunate – unfortunate
25. Behave – misbehave
26. Tolerant – intolerant
27. Appear – disappear
28. Honest – dishonest
29. Happy – sad
30. Young – elderly [8]

Exercise 1

Match 1,2,3.... with a, b, c according to their meaning.

- | | |
|--------------|--------------|
| 1. Misbehave | a. Elderly |
| 2. Sad | b. Dishonest |
| 3. Young | c. Fortunate |

- | | |
|----------------|----------------|
| 4. Intolerant | d. Behave |
| 5. Excusable | e. Appear |
| 6. Honest | f. Happy |
| 7. Unfortunate | g. Tolerant |
| 8. Disappear | h. inexcusable |

Answers: 1 d, 2 f, 3 a, 4 g, 5 h, 6 b, 7 c, 8 e.

Exercise 2

Complete the gaps with a word from the previous exercise. You should use an option only once.

1. The job is not as easy as it may _____.
2. It is _____ that young children were left in the house alone.
3. _____ to say, his grandfather has just died in the hospital.
4. Not all _____ can live with their family members because of several reasons.
5. Thank you for being so _____ with me in any cases.
6. John has a very _____ attitude towards other people.
7. It seems that not everyone is as _____ as we are.
8. A student has just finished a book which has a _____ ending.
9. He is a poor _____ person who invested in the company and now finds himself a few thousand pounds poorer.
10. Considering her difficult childhood her behavior is _____.
11. They often _____ differently when you are not around.
12. She can be very _____ of students who do not understand what she is talking about.
13. I do not like him, and it would be _____ of me to pretend otherwise.
14. This cottage would be perfect for a couple with a _____ family.
15. These forests could _____ altogether in the next twenty years by cutting down trees.
16. Some students have a tendency to _____ themselves at exam time because of having fear of failure.

Answers: 1 appear, 2 inexcusable, 3 sad, 4 elderly, 5 honest, 6 tolerant, 7 fortunate, 8 happy, 9 unfortunate, 10 excusable, 11 behave, 12 intolerant, 13 dishonest, 14 young, 15 disappear, 16 misbehave.

Exercise 3

Match the words with their correct definition.

Q1. 1) entrance 2) exit

- a. A way out of building, room, or passenger vehicle
- b. The opening, such as a door, passage, or gate that allows access of the place

Q2. 1) alive 2) dead

- a. Continuing in existence or use
- b. No longer alive

Q3. 1) borrow 2) lend

1. To take and use something belonging to someone else with the intention of returning it
2. To grant someone the use of something on the understanding that it will be returned

Q4. 1) give 2) receive

- a. To be given, presented with, or paid something
- b. (with two objects) freely transfer the possession of (something) to (someone)

Q5. 1) warm 2) cool

- a. Of or at a fairly low temperature
- b. Of or at a fairly or comfortably high temperature

Answers: Q1 (1 b, 2 a); Q2 (1 a, 2 b); Q3 (1 a, 2 b); Q4 (1 a, 2 b); Q5 (1 b, 2 a).

Exercise 4

Find the antonym of words in bold in order to correct the meaning of sentences.

1. How could she have been so **wise** as to fall in love with him.
2. Oh, you are so **fast**. Come on, hurry up.
3. People are likely to get **slim** if they eat so much chocolate.
4. We apologize for the **early** arrival of this train.
5. As you wrote a bad essay, it means you **pass** the exam.
6. The money never reached the people it was meant for but was stolen by **honest** officials.
7. It was **unlucky** for us that we were able to go fishing.
8. It gets **warm** in the evenings in November.
9. I tried to contact with him but I was **able** to.
10. Please, give up your seat to a **young** or disabled person.

Answers: 1. Foolish; 2. Slow; 3. Fat; 4. Late; 5. Fail; 6. Dishonest; 7. Lucky; 8. Cool; 9. Unable; 10. Elderly.

Exercise 5

Match the words in a box with their accurate definition.

a. Buy; b. Nonsense; c. Disappear; d. Lucky; e. False; f. Appear; g. Sell; h. Unlucky; i. Sense; j. True

- To cease to be visible.
- To obtain in exchange for payment.
- Not according with truth or fact or incorrect.
- Having, bringing, or resulting from good luck.
- To give or hand over something in exchange for money.
- Spoken or written words that have no meaning or make no sense.
- Having, bringing, or resulting from bad luck.
- To come into sight, become visible or noticeable, especially without apparent cause.
- In accordance with fact or reality.
- A faculty by which the body perceives an external stimulate.

Answers: 1 c, 2 a, 3 e, 4 e, 5 g, 6 b, 7 d, 8 f, 9 j, 10 i.

To recapitulate, the above mentioned the antonyms and we would clarify how they are crucially important for the English language learners. This article provides some of the antonyms and methods to enhance the knowledge of the learners in terms of this linguistics field. But it is noticeable that how one can work with them during learning in the future. Once a learner comes across a new word in another language, it is highly recommended to search their opposite meaning words. Eventually, they are likely to be familiar with most English antonyms in depth and with sophistication which leads them to seeing considerably high results. Alternatively, if a learner neglects learning antonyms, they will be disappointed because of a waste of time in the end. In order to avoid such an occasion, a student ought to keep in mind the importance of opposite meaning words.

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